

The Lorentz Invariance – 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the framework and intersecting it with the Lorentz invariance procedure given by special relativity, the author will construct additional analogous version of the equation on varying Lorentz manifolds, invoked stationary by the Euler Lagrange operator.

Introduction

In the 8T, the main equation (1) is describing a varying Einstein manifold, which is the connected manifold with (3,1) signature. The manifold was invoked stationary $M = M_0 \times R$ by an EL operator $L = (s, s', t)$ such a construction allowed us to derive equation (1.1) and the prediction of universe packets causing the outward time invariant acceleration.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M(1)} \frac{\partial M(1)}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} \frac{\partial s(n)}{\partial M(n)} \frac{\partial M(n)}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0$$

$$p_u = \frac{m_0 v_u}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (1.2)$$

as a summing variable for either one of the three spatial dimensions. What would be the analogous p_u version of this famous invariance in the 8T. It is an interesting question as we have no mass in our framework nor we have velocity. We do have arbitrary variations of the manifold vanishing into matter. Each matter entity causing the matrix to accelerate away from it as give by the main equation. as each matter entity is an amount of curvature. One would like to suggest a new version, whether correct or not, to the Lorentz invariance of special relativity.

$$\left| \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \right| \rightarrow \mathfrak{M} \quad (1.3)$$

$$p_u = \frac{|\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i| v_u}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_u^2}{c^2}}} \rightarrow \frac{\mathfrak{M} v_u}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_u^2}{c^2}}} \quad (1.31)$$

One will reason for this representation. The equation (1.31) is a replacement of the mass which do not present in the 8T. The meaning is the following: take the total amount of arbitrary variations as a replacement of mass constructing the object. Such a variation will have twofold affects. The first, is much more accurate prediction, the other is more complexity as requires decomposing an object to the exact amount of numerical components. Additional difference is that the speed variable has lower index now as a classification measure for the spatial dimension in hand. It was not presented in the special relativity original form.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)